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Review Article

**A REVIEW OF PHYTOCHEMICALS WITH ANTIDEPRESSANT
PROPERTIES****Miss. Poojitha Gindi ¹, Mrs. Y. Chandravadana ², Mr. Dr. Venu Gopal ³**¹Final Year B Pharmacy, Krishna Teja Pharmacy college, Tirupati -517506.²Associate professor, Department of pharmacology, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati - 517506.³Professor and Principal, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati -517506.**Abstract:**

Depression is a prevalent and debilitating mental health disorder that affects millions globally, with significant impacts on individuals' quality of life and well-being. While conventional antidepressants are widely used, there is growing interest in the potential of phytochemicals natural compounds found in plants as alternative treatments for depression. These plant-based compounds, including flavonoids, alkaloids, and terpenes, exhibit antidepressant-like properties through mechanisms such as neurotransmitter modulation, anti-inflammatory effects, and neuroprotection. Phytochemicals like Hypericum perforatum (St. John's Wort), Bacopa monnieri, and Rhodiola rosea have shown promise in reducing depressive symptoms with fewer side effects compared to synthetic drugs. Other plants, such as lavender, chamomile, and turmeric, contain bioactive substances that support mood regulation and stress reduction. Despite the potential benefits, challenges remain in standardizing plant extracts and ensuring their safety and efficacy through rigorous clinical studies. This article explores the role of various phytochemicals in managing depression, highlighting both their therapeutic advantages and limitations. The findings underscore the need for further research to validate these natural remedies and integrate them into holistic treatment approaches for depression, offering a complementary option alongside traditional therapies.

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INTRODUCTION:

Depression is a complex neuropsychiatric condition with significant morbidity, mortality and disability. It is a mental and brain disorder characterized by the signs and symptoms such as, Persistent sad, anxious, Inability of concentration, Weight gain or loss, Agitation, Fatigue or loss of energy, Insomnia or hypersomnia, Diminished interest or pleasure, Thought of suicide or death, Guilt, worthlessness, Irritability, and frustration(1).

An estimated 3.8% of people suffer from depression, including 5.7% of individuals older than 60years and 5% of adults. Depression affects over 280 million people worldwide. Women are around 50% more likely than men to experience depression. More over 10% of expectant mothers and recent mothers experience depression globally. An estimated 7laks people lose their lives to suicide each year. The fourth

most common cause of mortality for people aged 15 to 29 years.

Although there are effective treatments for mental disorders, more than 75% of people in low- and middle-income countries receive no treatment. Barriers to effective care include a lack of investment in mental health care, a lack of trained healthcare providers, and social stigma associated with mental disorders(2).

TYPES

Types of Depression:

1. Major Depressive Disorder (MDD):
2. Persistent Depressive Disorder:
3. Bipolar Disorder (Manic Depression):
4. Postpartum Depression:
5. Seasonal Affective Disorder (SAD):
6. Psychotic Depression:

Types of depression					
	Major depressive disorder	Persistent depressive disorder	Bipolar disorder	Post natal depression	Premenstrual dysphoric disorder
Also known as	Clinical depression	Dysthymia	Manic depression	Postpartum depression	Premenstrual dysphoria
Characterised by	Prolonged feelings of sadness for more than two weeks	Depression symptoms that last at least two years	Extreme fluctuations in mood and energy	Feeling depressed for several weeks after giving birth	More severe than premenstrual syndrome

1. Major Depressive Disorder (MDD):

- It is also known as clinical depression; this is characterized by a persistent feeling of sadness or a lack of interest in life for at least two weeks. Symptoms can be severe enough to impact work, sleep, eating, and social functioning(3).

2. Persistent Depressive Disorder:

- It is also known as called Dysthymia. Less severe symptoms that last for a long time, often for several years(4).

3. Bipolar Disorder (Manic Depression):

- bipolar disorder, is depressive episodes alternate with periods of manic symptoms, which include euphoria or irritability, increased activity and energy(5).

4. Postpartum Depression:

- Depression that affects some women after giving birth(6).

5. Seasonal Affective Disorder (SAD):

- This type of depression occurs seasonally, usually during the winter months when there is less sunlight. People with SAD often feel lethargic and have low energy(7).

6. Psychotic Depression:

- This severe form of depression is combined with psychosis, which can include delusions (false beliefs) or hallucinations (hearing or seeing things that aren't there)(8).

Causes of Depression:

Depression can result from a complex factor:

Biological Factors**a) Genetics:**

A family history of depression can increase an individual's risk of developing the condition, indicating a hereditary component.

b) Brain Chemistry:

Imbalances in neurotransmitters such as serotonin, dopamine, and norepinephrine, which regulate mood, can contribute to depression

c) Hormonal Imbalances:

Changes in hormone levels, such as during pregnancy, postpartum, menopause, or thyroid disorders, can trigger depression.

Psychological Factors**a) Personality Traits:**

people who are generally low self-esteem or more pessimistic may be more susceptible to depression.

b) Cognitive Patterns:

Negative thought patterns, can lead to feelings of hopelessness and despair.

Environmental Factors

a) Life Events:

Stressful or Traumatic experiences, like death of a loved one's, divorce, job loss, or financial difficulties.

b) Social Support system:

Loneliness, lack of social support, or feelings of isolation can contribute to the development of depression.

c) Substance Abuse:

Alcohol and drug use can cause the chemical imbalances in the brain leads to depression

Substance Abuse and Addiction

Alcohol, recreational drugs, or prescription medication misuse can lead to depression, due to the direct effects on brain because of the social and emotional consequences of addiction.

Lack of Sleep

Sleep disorders, insomnia, or poor-quality sleep can contribute to depression by impairing mood, energy levels, and cognitive abilities.

Nutritional Deficiencies

Depression symptoms have been linked to poor food, deficits in particular vitamins (such as B12 folate), or low levels of omega-3 fatty acids.

Seasonal Factors

a) Seasonal Affective Disorder (SAD):

Depression occurs during specific seasons, usually in the winter months when there is less sunlight, which can disrupt circadian rhythms and affect serotonin levels(10).

ANTIDEPRESSANTS

Antidepressants are those drugs, which are used for the treatment of depressive illness. These are also called as mood elevators or thymoleptics potentially directly or indirectly the action on dopamine, serotonin, noradrenaline and increase the neurotransmitters in the synapse. They can be used alone or in combination with other medications(12).

Advantages and Challenges of Phytochemicals as Antidepressants

The main advantage of phytochemical-based antidepressants is their natural origin, which may

result in fewer side effects compared to synthetic drugs. Additionally, many phytochemicals have multifaceted mechanisms of action, potentially offering a more holistic approach to treating

depression. They can target various aspects of brain chemistry and neurobiology, including neurotransmitter regulation, neuroprotection, stress response, and inflammation.

However, there are several challenges to the widespread use of phytochemicals as antidepressants. One major concern is the variability in the potency and composition of plant extracts. Unlike synthetic drugs, which are precisely formulated and standardized, plant extracts can vary significantly in their active ingredient concentrations depending on factors like growing conditions, harvesting methods, and processing techniques. Moreover, the safety and long-term efficacy of many phytochemicals remain understudied, and clinical trials are needed to confirm their therapeutic value(13).

ROLE OF PHYTOCHEMICALS IN ANTIDEPRESSANTS THERAPY

Phytochemicals, naturally occurring compounds found in plants, have shown promising potential in the development of antidepressants. Unlike traditional synthetic antidepressants, phytochemical-based antidepressants leverage the bioactive properties of these plant-derived compounds, which can influence

various biochemical pathways related to mood regulation. Many phytochemicals, including flavonoids, alkaloids, and terpenes, exhibit properties such as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and neuroprotective effects that may contribute to mood stabilization and relief from depressive symptoms.

Advantage of phytochemical-based antidepressants is their relatively lower risk of adverse side effects compared to some conventional medications. For instance, plants like *Hypericum perforatum* (St. John's Wort) and compounds like curcumin from turmeric have been studied for their antidepressant effects. These compounds are believed to modulate neurotransmitters such as serotonin, dopamine, and norepinephrine, similar to synthetic antidepressants, but often through multiple pathways, potentially offering a more holistic approach to treatment.

The chemical ingredients present in many plants including several vegetables and fruits have been found to act as potential antidepressants. They also treat a variety of conditions, such as cardiovascular, autoimmune, and neurological disorders, with great cost-effectiveness, safety, and efficacy.

These phytochemicals possess antidepressants like properties:

PHYTOCHEMICALS	PLANTS	ADVERSE EFFECTS	USES	REFERENCES
1) Linalool	Lavender (<i>Lavender Angustifolia</i>)	Skin and eye irritation Respiratory tract irritation	Antidepressant Neuroprotective effect	14
2) Lemon balm	<i>Melissa officinalis</i>	Dizziness Sedation Anxiety	Reduce stress Anxiety Improve appetite Discomfort from indigestion	15
3) Omega-3-fatty acids	Flaxseeds (<i>Linum usitatissimum</i>)	Diarrhoea Constipation Abnormal pain	Postpartum depression Anxiety	16
4) s-adenosyl methionine (SAME)	Garlic (<i>Allium sativum</i>)	Anxiety Restlessness Insomnia	Depression Liver disease Osteoarthritis	17
5) Ursolic acid	Rosemary	Indigestion Dizziness Diarrhoea	Enhances stress resistance Neural dysfunction	18
6) Eugenol	<i>Oscimum sanctum</i>	Diarrhoea	Anxiety Stomach upset	19
7) Alkaloids	<i>Withania somnifera</i>	GIT disturbance	Stabilization of moods	20

8) Chlorogenic acid	Green coffee	DNA damage	Relieve depression	21
9) Berberine	Berberis vulgaris	Constipation Upset stomach	Relieving depression	22
10) Astaxanthin	Microalgae (Haematococcus pluvialis)	Increased bowel movements	Antioxidants Cardiovascular	23
11) Sulforaphane	Broccoli	Gastrointestinal discomfort	Mood and cognitive function	24
12) Indole-3-carbinol	Cruciferous vegetables	Balance problems, Diarrhoea,	Chronic depression Oxidative stress	25
13) Piper nigrum	Black pepper	Digestive issues	Antioxidant Antidepressant	26
14) Naringenin	Grape fruit	GIT issues Fatigue	Antioxidant	27
15) Theobromine	Cocoa (Theobroma cocoa)	Digestive issues	Mild depressive effect	28
16) Acetyl-L-carnitine	Alfalfa (Medicago sativa)	Diarrhoea, Nausea, Stomach pain.	Decrease the depression Improve memory	29
17) 5-HTP	Griffonia simplicifolia	Heartburn, Stomach pain,	Less evidence for insomnia	30
18) Kava	Piper methysticum	Drowsiness, Anxiety, Insomnia.	Anxiety Stress relief	31
19) Saponins	Bacopa monnieri	Anxiety Agitation Insomnia	Depression Anxiety Memory loss	32
20) Gentisic acid	Gentian	Skin irritation drowsiness	Bipolar depression Schizophrenia	33
21) Punicalagin	Pomegranate	Skin inflammation Stomach upset	Oxidative stress Anxiety reduction Memory protection	34
22) Sinapic acid	Brassica juncea	GIT issues	Anxiety	35
23) Ferulic acid	Ferula Asafoetida	Loss of Appetite Diarrhoea	Oxidative stress Respiratory irritation	36
24) phosphatidylserine	soybean	GIT issues	Mood enhancement	37
25) Flavonoids	Glycyrrhiza uralensis	Mutagens Pro-oxidants	Anti-oxidants irritants Skin	38
26) Glycosides	Apocynum venetum	Anxiety GIT upset	Pro-oxidants DNA damage	39
27) Terpenoids	Chamomile adalah	Coma Mental status	Anxiety GIT upset	40
28) Quercetin	Apples	Upset stomach headache	GIT issues Seizures	41
29) Resveratrol	Grapes	Liver dysfunction Abdominal pain	Stomach upset Headache	42

OSMIMUM SANCTUM

Osmium sanctum (holy basil or Tulsi) is a revered herb in traditional medicine, particularly in Ayurveda, for its mood-stabilizing and stress-reducing effects. Rich in bioactive compounds like eugenol, ursolic acid, and flavonoids, Tulsi has been shown to exert adaptogenic properties, helping the body cope with stress. Studies suggest that it can reduce cortisol levels, a hormone linked to stress and depression, and enhance the production of neurotransmitters like serotonin and dopamine. By combating oxidative stress and inflammation, Osmium sanctum offers potential antidepressant-like effects, supporting mental well-being and providing relief from symptoms of anxiety and depression(19).

MELISSA OFFICINALIS

Melissa officinalis (lemon balm) is a medicinal herb known for its calming and mood-enhancing properties. Traditionally used to reduce anxiety and improve sleep, lemon balm contains bioactive compounds like rosmarinic acid and flavonoids, which have demonstrated antidepressant-like effects in clinical studies. These compounds help regulate neurotransmitter activity, particularly GABA, serotonin, and dopamine, which are involved in mood regulation. By reducing anxiety, enhancing cognitive function, and promoting relaxation, Melissa officinalis may provide natural relief from symptoms of depression. Its mild sedative and neuroprotective effects make it a valuable adjunct to managing mood disorders(15).

CHAMOMILE ADALAH

Chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla*) is a well-known herb with calming and antidepressant-like properties. Rich in apigenin, a flavonoid with anxiolytic and sedative effects, chamomile has been traditionally used to alleviate anxiety, promote relaxation, and improve sleep quality—key factors in managing depression. Studies suggest that chamomile extracts may help modulate serotonin and other neurotransmitters involved in mood regulation. Its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties further support its potential as a natural antidepressant by reducing oxidative stress, a contributing factor to depression. Chamomile offers a gentle, natural alternative for easing depressive symptoms and promoting emotional well-being without the side effects of many pharmaceuticals(40).

BACOPA MONNIERI

Bacopa monnieri, also known as Brahmi, is an adaptogenic herb widely used in Ayurvedic medicine for its cognitive and mood-enhancing properties. It contains active compounds like bacosides, which are believed to modulate neurotransmitter activity, including serotonin and dopamine—key players in mood regulation. Research suggests that Bacopa monnieri may reduce symptoms of anxiety and depression by promoting neuroprotection, enhancing memory, and improving the brain's stress response. Its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects also contribute to its antidepressant-like benefits. As a natural remedy, Bacopa monnieri offers potential as a gentle, effective supplement for alleviating mood disorders and supporting mental health(32).

HYPERICUM PERFORATUM

Hypericum perforatum (St. John's wort) is one of the most studied herbal treatments for depression. It contains active compounds like hypericin and hyperforin, which are believed to exert antidepressant effects by modulating neurotransmitter systems, particularly serotonin, dopamine, and norepinephrine. These compounds may inhibit the reuptake of these neurotransmitters, similar to the action of conventional antidepressants like SSRIs. St. John's wort has shown efficacy in treating mild to moderate depression, with studies suggesting it may be as effective as pharmaceutical antidepressants, but with fewer side effects(37).

GRAPES

Grapes, particularly red and purple varieties, contain potent antioxidants such as resveratrol and flavonoids that have been studied for their potential antidepressant-like effects. These compounds help reduce inflammation and oxidative stress, which are linked to the development of depression. Resveratrol, in particular, has been shown to enhance the function of neurotransmitters like serotonin and dopamine, which play key roles in mood regulation. Studies suggest that the antioxidants in grapes may also promote neurogenesis and protect the brain from stress-induced damage. While not a substitute for conventional treatments, grapes and their compounds may offer natural support for mental health and mood improvement(42).

FLAXSEEDS

Flaxseeds are rich in omega-3 fatty acids, particularly alpha-linolenic acid (ALA), which has been linked to mood regulation and antidepressant effects. Omega-3s play a key role in maintaining brain health by supporting neurotransmitter function and reducing inflammation—both of which are involved in depression. Studies suggest that ALA may help increase serotonin and dopamine levels, improve cognitive function, and enhance overall emotional well-being. Additionally, flaxseeds are high in lignans, which have antioxidant properties that can reduce oxidative stress in the brain. Incorporating flaxseeds into the diet may help alleviate mild depressive symptoms and support mental health(16).

LAVENDER

Lavender (*Lavandula angustifolia*) is widely known for its calming and mood-enhancing properties. It contains essential oils, particularly linalool and linalyl acetate, which have been shown to reduce anxiety, promote relaxation, and alleviate symptoms of depression. Research indicates that lavender's calming effects help regulate neurotransmitters like serotonin and gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), both of which are involved in mood regulation. Studies suggest that lavender oil, when used in aromatherapy or as a supplement, may provide mild antidepressant effects, reduce anxiety, and improve sleep quality. Lavender offers a natural, non-invasive remedy for managing stress and depressive symptoms(14).

GARLIC

Garlic (*Allium sativum*) is not only valued for its health benefits but also for its potential antidepressant-like effects. Rich in sulfur compounds, particularly allicin, garlic has anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and neuroprotective properties. These properties help reduce oxidative stress and inflammation, which are linked to depression. Some studies suggest that garlic can enhance brain function by improving the levels of serotonin and dopamine—neurotransmitters crucial for mood regulation. Additionally, garlic may reduce cortisol, the stress hormone, helping to balance the body's stress response. While more research is needed, garlic's natural compounds may provide a supportive role in managing depressive symptoms(17).

VALERIAN

Valerian (*Valeriana officinalis*) is an herb known for its calming and sedative effects, commonly used to alleviate anxiety and insomnia. It contains active compounds like valerenic acid, which interact with GABA receptors in the brain, helping to promote relaxation and reduce stress. Studies suggest that valerian may have mild antidepressant effects by reducing anxiety, improving sleep quality, and promoting a balanced mood. Its ability to calm the nervous system may also help regulate neurotransmitter activity, including serotonin and dopamine. While valerian is primarily used for its sedative properties, it may offer natural support for managing mild depression and stress-related symptoms(20).

RHODIOLA ROSEA L

Rhodiola rosea, also known as golden root, is an adaptogenic herb traditionally used to combat fatigue and stress. It contains active compounds like rosavin and salidroside, which help regulate the body's stress response by balancing cortisol levels and enhancing the activity of neurotransmitters such as serotonin, dopamine, and norepinephrine. These effects make *Rhodiola rosea* a potential natural antidepressant, particularly for individuals experiencing stress-induced depression or burnout. Research suggests that it can improve mood, reduce anxiety, and enhance mental clarity. *Rhodiola*'s adaptogenic properties help the body adapt to stress, making it a valuable herb for supporting overall emotional well-being(27).

GINKGO BILOBA

Ginkgo biloba, a popular herbal supplement, is known for its potential cognitive-enhancing and mood-boosting effects. It contains active compounds like flavonoids and terpenoids, which have antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, helping to protect brain cells from oxidative stress. Studies suggest that *Ginkgo biloba* may improve blood circulation to the brain, which could enhance the delivery of oxygen and nutrients, supporting better brain function and mood regulation. Research also indicates that it may modulate serotonin and dopamine levels, neurotransmitters associated with depression. While it's not a primary treatment for depression, *Ginkgo biloba* may offer mild antidepressant effects, especially in conjunction with other therapies(29).

CROCUS SATIVUS

Crocus sativus, commonly known as saffron, has gained attention for its potential antidepressant properties. The active compounds in saffron, particularly safranal and crocin, have been shown to influence neurotransmitter systems, including serotonin, dopamine, and norepinephrine, which are essential for mood regulation. Several studies suggest that saffron may be as effective as conventional antidepressants in treating mild to moderate depression, with fewer side effects. Its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties also help combat oxidative stress; a factor linked to depression. Regular consumption of saffron, either as a supplement or in food, may help alleviate symptoms of depression and enhance overall well-being(21).

FERILLA FRUTESCENS

Perilla frutescens, commonly known as perilla or Chinese basil, is an herb with potential antidepressant-like effects. Rich in omega-3 fatty acids (especially alpha-linolenic acid) and flavonoids, perilla has anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties that support brain health. Research suggests that its omega-3 content may help regulate neurotransmitters like serotonin and dopamine, which are crucial for mood stabilization. Perilla's anti-inflammatory effects may also reduce the neuroinflammation often linked to depression. Some studies have shown that perilla may alleviate symptoms of anxiety and depression by modulating the stress response, making it a promising natural adjunct for mood enhancement and mental well-being(34).

WITHANIA SOMNIFERA

Withania somnifera (commonly known as Ashwagandha) is an adaptogenic herb often used to manage stress, anxiety, and depression. When combined with antidepressant medications, it may provide synergistic benefits due to its ability to regulate cortisol levels, reduce stress, and improve mood. Some studies suggest Ashwagandha can enhance the effectiveness of antidepressants like SSRIs or SNRIs, potentially improving overall well-being and reducing side effects. However, caution is advised as Ashwagandha may interact with certain medications, altering their effects or increasing the risk of side effects. Always consult a healthcare provider before combining it with antidepressant treatment(20).

PIPER METHYSTICUM

Piper methysticum commonly known as Kava-Kava is consumed as a ritual stimulant; large doses cause intoxication. The standardized extract of kava-kava roots are used for the therapy of anxiety, tension, insomnia and restlessness. Kava pyrones, the major constituents of kava-kava, are generally considered to be responsible for the pharmacological activity in humans and animals. The inhibition of MAO-B by kava pyrones-enriched extract might be an important mechanism for their psychotropic activity(31).

ROSEMARY

Rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*) is an herb known for its potential to enhance mood and cognitive function. It may have mild antidepressant-like effects due to its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, which support brain health. While it's not a substitute for antidepressant medications, rosemary can complement treatment by promoting relaxation and improving memory. However, caution is advised when combining it with antidepressants, especially those affecting serotonin or other neurotransmitters, as rosemary may interact with certain medications, altering their effects or increasing side effects. Always consult a healthcare provider before using rosemary alongside antidepressant therapy to avoid potential interactions(18).

CONCLUSION:

Depression is a multifaceted condition that affects millions worldwide, with a profound impact on quality of life. While traditional antidepressants remain a primary treatment option, the growing interest in natural remedies, particularly phytochemicals, offers a promising alternative. Phytochemicals derived from plants like *Hypericum perforatum* (St. John's Wort), *Bacopa monnieri* (Brahmi), *Melissa officinalis* (lemon balm), and *Lavandula angustifolia* (lavender) have demonstrated potential antidepressant properties through their neuroprotective, anti-inflammatory, and mood-regulating effects. These natural compounds often act by modulating neurotransmitters such as serotonin, dopamine, and norepinephrine, which are critical for mood stabilization.

The advantages of phytochemicals include fewer side effects compared to synthetic antidepressants, as well as their holistic approach to mental well-being. However, challenges such as variability in potency, lack of standardized formulations, and the need for more clinical trials persist. Despite these hurdles, plant-based antidepressants show promise in complementing traditional treatments for depression. By offering a natural, effective, and safe alternative, phytochemicals could play a significant role in the future of depression therapy, contributing to better mental health outcomes for those suffering from this debilitating condition.

REFERENCE:

- Spitzer RL, Endicott J, Robins E (1975). "The development of diagnostic criteria in psychiatry" archived from the original on 14 December 2005. Retrieved 8 November 2008.
- Gin Malhi S, John Mann J. Depression. *Lancet* 2018; 392:2299-12.
- Woody CA, Ferrari AJ, Siskind DJ, Whiteford HA, Harris MG. A systematic review and meta-regression of the prevalence and incidence of perinatal depression. *J Affect Disord*. 2017; 219:86-92.
- Schramm E, Klein DN, Elsaesser M, Furukawa TA, Domschke K. Review of dysthymia and persistent depressive disorder: history, correlates, and clinical implications. *Lancet Psychiatry*. 2020 Sep;7(9):801-812.
- McIntyre RS, Berk M, Brietzke E, Goldstein BI, López-Jaramillo C, Kessing LV, Malhi GS, Nierenberg AA, Rosenblat JD, Majeed A, Vieta E, Vinberg M, Young AH, Mansur RB. Bipolar disorders. *Lancet*. 2020 Dec 05;396(10265):1841-1856.
- Hutcherson TC, Cieri-Hutcherson NE, Gosciak MF. Brexanolone for postpartum depression. *Am J Health Syst Pharm*. 2020 Feb 19;77(5):336-345.
- Fonte A, Coutinho B. Seasonal sensitivity and psychiatric morbidity: study about seasonal affective disorder. *BMC Psychiatry*. 2021 Jun 29;21(1):317.
- Guze SB, Woodruff RA Jr, Clayton PJ. The significance of psychotic affective disorders. *Arch Gen Psychiatry*. 1975 Sep;32(9):1147-50.
- American Psychiatric Association. *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Second Edition*. 2 ed. Washington, D.C.: American Psychiatric Press, Inc.; 1968.
- Behl T, Rana T, Sehgal A, Sharma N, Albarrati A, Albratty M, Makeen HA, Najmi A, Verma R, Bungau SG. Prog Neuropsychopharmacology *Biol Psychiatry*. 2023 Apr 20; 123:110693. doi: 10.1016/j.pnpbp.2022.110693. Epub 2022 Dec 9. PMID: 36509251.
- Lulu Cui, Shu Li, Major depressive disorder: hypothesis, mechanism, prevention and treatment 9,30;2024.
- Fasipe O (2018). Neuropharmacological classification of antidepressant agents based on their mechanism of action. *Neuropharmacological archives of medicine and health sciences*.6(1):81.doi:10.4103/amhs.7-18.
- Atanas G. Atanasov, Natural products in drug discovery: advances and opportunities.20,200-216(2021).
- Dos Santos, linalool as a therapeutic and medicinal tool in depression treatment: a review current neuropharmacology 2022, pp 1073-1092.
- Shih-Hang Lin, A medicinal herb, *Melissa officinalis* L. ameliorates depressive-like behavior of rats in the forced swimming test via regulating the serotonergic neurotransmitter. *ethnopharmacology* 2015,4-175.
- Arshad Uddin Ahmed Syed, Assessment of antidepressant activity of omega 3 fatty acids in rodents. *pharmacology* 2018,12-7.
- Alessandro Cuomo s-Adenosylmethionine (SAME) in major depressive disorder (MDD): a clinician-oriented systematic review.2020, 5-19.
- Imran Kazmi, Anticonvulsant and depressant-like activity of ursolic acid stearyl glucoside isolated from *Lantana camara* L. (verbanaceae). 2012,7-12.
- Shivananjappa M, Joshi M. Aqueous extract of Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*) enhances endogenous antioxidant defenses of human hepatoma cell line (HepG2) *J Herbs Spices Med Plants*. 2012; 18:331-48.

20. K.G. Lloyd et al. Neuropsychopharmacol. Biol. Psychiat 1989.
21. Soo-Hyun Park, Antidepressant-like effect of chlorogenic acid isolated from *Artemisia capillaris* Thunb.2010,12-14.
22. Shrinivas K. Kulkarni, On the mechanism of antidepressant-like action of berberine chloride.2008,28-589.
23. Yuting Ke, Preventive and Therapeutic Effects of Astaxanthin on Depressive-Like Behaviors in High-Fat Diet and Streptozotocin-Treated Rats. *neuropharmacology* 2020,30-10.
24. Pablo Ferreira-Chamorro, Sulforaphane Inhibited the Nociceptive Responses, Anxiety- and Depressive-Like Behaviors Associated with Neuropathic Pain and Improved the Anti-allodynic Effects of Morphine in Mice. *pharmacology* 2018,20-9.
25. Reem N. El-Naga, Effects of indole-3-carbinol on clonidine-induced neurotoxicity in rats: Impact on oxidative stress, inflammation, apoptosis and monoamine levels. *Pharmacology* 2014,19-44.
26. Al Mamun, Evaluation of CNS depressant and analgesic activities of the methanol extract of *piper longum* linn. leaves. *pharmacy*2011,27-2.
27. Solomon umukoro, Naringenin attenuates behavioral derangements induced by social defeat stress in mice via inhibition of acetylcholinesterase activity, oxidative stress and release of pro-inflammatory cytokines. *neuropharmacology*2018-105.
28. Carlo Tenore Coffee and Depression: A Short Review of Literature. *current pharmaceutical design*.2015,21.
29. Jagamohan Padhy, Antidepressant Effect of Acetyl-L-Carnitine and Bupropion against Experimental Animal Model. *department of pharmacy* 2024,30-16.
30. Alhasan Sabah Mansour, Assessment of Antidepressant Profile of Methanolic extract of *Areca catechu* using Mice as an experimental Model .2021,15-35.
31. Clare stevinson, A systematic review of safety of kava extract in the treatment of anxiety.2012,21-25.
32. H Dang, Y Chen, X Liu, Q Wang, Antidepressant effects of ginseng total saponins in the forced swimming test and chronic mild stress models of depression,2009.
33. Arthur Osol, A Physicochemical Study of Gentisic Acid.1952,6-41.
34. Padmaja Kalshetti, Antidepressant and Anti-Anxiety Effect of Ellagic Acid from *Punica granatum* L. Rind in Olfactory Bulbectomy Model in Rats.*pharmacology*.2015 31-32.
35. Bansal Sudha, Behavioral,biochemical and histopathological evaluation of sinapic acid for antidepressant activity in mice and stressed mice.2023,2-16.
36. Xiaoyu Dong, Ferulic acid: An extraordinarily neuroprotective phenolic acid with anti-depressive properties. *neurology*,2022-105.
37. Maria c.olianas, inhibition of TNF-alpha induced neuronal apoptosis by antidepressants acting through the lysophosphatidic acid receptor LPA1,2019-24.
38. Haroon khan, Current standing of plant derived flavonoids as an antidepressant.2018-119.
39. Haroon khan, Targeting BDNF modulation by plant glycosides as a novel therapeutic strategy in the treatment of depression.2018-196.
40. Mariana meckes, Terpenoids Isolated from *Psidium guajava* Hexane Extract with Depressant Activity on Central Nervous System.1996-10.
41. Muragundla anjaneulu, Antidepressant Activity of Quercetin, a Bioflavonoid, in Streptozotocin-Induced Diabetic Mice.2006-41.
42. Yingcong yua, the anti-depressant effects of a novel PDE4 inhibitor derived from resveratrol.2020-59.